

Green Hydrogen: Measuring imaginaries and promises in peripheral contexts. An analysis of policies, papers and news in Argentina and Mexico

Methodological Annexes

Annex I: Analytical structure of Imaginaries and promises

For the classification and analysis of technoscientific imaginaries and promises in the three types of documents (news, papers, and policies), we developed the following structure of analytical categories of imaginaries and their correspondence with technoscientific promises.

Table I: Analytical structure of Imaginaries and their correspondence with technoscientific promises

Imaginaries	Promises
1. Technoscientific	1.1 Techno-scientific
2. Economic	2.1 Production
	2.2 Local development & Integration
	2.3 Infrastructure
3. Politic	3.1 Employment
	3.2 Administration
	3.3 Industrial policy
4. Environmental	4.1 Environmental
5. Energetic	5.1 Clean energy
6. Geopolitic	6.1 Investments & Projects
	6.2 International insertion
	6.3 Climate commitments

Description of the Imaginaries used for document classification.

1. **Technoscientific:** This imaginary refers to the scientific, technological and innovative development to be deployed around HV. This involves the deployment of different types of technologies, the scientific and technical orientation of human resources, the search for technological and process efficiency and optimization, and significant growth in scientific production focused on HV worldwide.
 - 1.1. **Technoscientific:** This includes actions or goals related to the involvement of the scientific and technological sector; financing or investment plans for STI projects; and the development of technologies, materials and/or processes (including socio-technical ones). Reference to types of technology involved in the production of HV.

2. **Economic:** In this imaginary, HV technologies occupies a priority place on the political and economic agendas of the world's major economies, international organizations and multinational companies. For developing countries, it is seen as an opportunity for economic and productive growth and/or recovery. This envisages imminent national development, the federal integration of regions with productive potential, integration into the regional and global economy, and competitive entry into a new green economy and market, with the possibility of accessing substantial investment. The most common expectations include the deployment of the various parties involved in the value chain, the promotion of new local and territorial economies, the emergence of public and private stakeholders, and the construction of infrastructure for storing and transporting HV.
 - 2.1. **Production:** references to industrial aspects, large-scale production and the anticipated stages. Also covered are competitiveness, production costs, transportation, the identification of hydrogen target sectors, port construction, technological and production capacities, and the emergence of new public and private actors.
 - 2.2. **Local development and integration:** refers to policies with specific local development objectives that enable the deployment of different economic sectors, as well as regional coordination and inclusion. It also includes the mention of geographically optimal locations, territorial development and goals with a federal perspective, such as connectivity to ports, the promotion of new local sectors (such as tourism) and the opening of new productive and industrial sectors. These policies also include actions to supply the domestic market.
 - 2.3. **Infrastructure:** development and analysis of sectors and technologies that require investment in order to optimize the hydrogen industry.
3. **Politic:** This imaginary involves government sectors making decisions at different internal levels on matters such as governance and sovereignty over natural resources, compliance with international commitments, project implementation, investment in science, technology and innovation, infrastructure, legislation, certifications, employability and social inclusion goals, public–private coordination, creating new state actors and conducting socio-environmental assessments. Significant actions include signing collaborative and certification agreements related to developing the hydrogen economy and establishing national strategies and roadmaps for implementing this new vector in national economies.
 - 3.1. **Employment:** Promotion of job skills in green employment, job estimates, identification of key sectors, employment goals for local communities, involvement of trade unions, socioeconomic profitability objectives and training in technical and professional education for specialized resources in HV.
 - 3.2. **Administration:** It involves promises related to the administration and management of the value chain in the developing energy sector. This includes the research and development of technical knowledge for managing the sector.
 - 3.3. **Industrial policy:** The institutional political role of the different levels in relation to regulations, certification, legislation and feasibility assessments for project installation, as well as the recognition of uncertainties and investments in key

sectors. Energy sovereignty, energy security, equity, policy deployment and strategic planning in sectors involving hydrogen; guarantees of public information; regular reports on the state's role in the sector; and the creation of focused government entities.

4. **Environment:** This imaginary points to environmental and climate sustainability in energy production processes and is why it encompasses not only the physical production of energy, which must be based on renewable sources, but also social aspects such as environmental education, the participation of local communities in government decisions, guarantees for local energy supply, access to public information on projects, care for ecosystems, warnings of risks and uncertainties, among others.
 - 4.1. **Environment:** international commitments to mitigating climate change, policies addressing socio-environmental sustainability and the sustainability of renewable energies, decarbonization goals, the deployment of aspects related to the just transition, environmental education, citizen participation objectives, energy planning taking socio-environmental needs into account.
5. **Energetic:** This imaginary scenario focuses on energy security and sustaining current global energy production while gradually shifting away from conventional fossil fuel sources towards renewable ones. The aim is to supply the sectors with the highest energy consumption, such as heavy industry and transportation, with energy.
 - 5.1. **Clean energy:** technological, political and economic objectives involving an increased use of renewable energy sources in the energy system, greater prominence for renewable energy sources in the energy matrix, energy efficiency measures, decarbonization targets and greenhouse gas (GHG) emission reduction targets.
6. **Geopolitic:** It refers to a new global technological, political, economic and financial landscape in which developed countries have mapped out the hydrogen economy and its value chain for international trade and energy supply. Countries are positioned as exporters, consumers and self-sufficient producers, leading to the establishment and reorganization of governance lines for states and the hegemonic business sector in the emerging hydrogen market and its variants. International organizations play a leading role in this scenario through the publication of specialized documents, climate commitments, national strategy publications by states, bilateral agreements, new public and private partnerships, hydrogen production projects using different technologies, financial reorientation, the rise of renewable energy technologies, investment in science, technology and innovation sectors, and the establishment of short-, medium- and long-term goals.
 - 6.1. **Projects and investments:** identification of strategic partners; international relations with organizations and states; loans; external promotion; promotion of partnerships and cooperation with companies and institutions; green bonds; carbon markets.

- 6.2. **International integration:** hydrogen geopolitics; commercialization; cooperation; energy security; bilateral agreements; transnational legislation; and the signing of agreements with international governmental and non-governmental organizations.
- 6.3. **Climate commitments:** planning with short-, medium- and long-term goals, based on international commitments such as the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), the Paris Agreement and reducing GHG emissions.

Annex II: Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA)

Full method description

The Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA) model is part of Natural Language Processing (NLP) techniques, a field of computer science that seeks to enable computer systems to interpret and process human language (Bird, Klein, & Loper, 2009). It is an unsupervised machine learning method that allows patterns and thematic structures to be identified in large volumes of textual data (Ejaz, Ittefaq & Jamil, 2023). It is based on a generative probabilistic model in which each document is conceived as a combination of latent topics, while each topic is defined by a distribution of words (Blei, Ng & Jordan, 2003).

The main advantages of LDA include its ability to discover regularities in texts without prior training, identify co-occurrences of words that reveal shared meanings and classify documents into multiple topics flexibly (Ejaz et al., 2023; Piñeyrúa, 2021). However, there are also limitations. For example, the number of topics must be set in advance, which involves testing different configurations until the most appropriate one is found (Grün & Hornik, 2011). Additionally, it is based on the 'bag of words' assumption, which ignores the sequence and syntactic context of terms (Ejaz et al., 2023).

The model operates on two main parameters: Gamma, representing the probability of a topic in a document, and Beta, indicating the probability of a word in a topic (Piñeyrúa, 2021). Additionally, model quality is evaluated using coherence, a metric that measures the semantic consistency of the words that comprise each topic. This facilitates the selection of the most robust and comprehensible configuration (Grün & Hornik, 2011).

LDA is based on a series of fundamental assumptions. Firstly, topics are latent entities; that is to say, they are not explicitly defined in the texts, but rather are inferred from patterns of word co-occurrence (Ejaz et al., 2023). It is also assumed that words tend to appear together, leaving traces of meaning that allow thematic groups to be formed. Another central assumption is that the number of themes is unknown in advance, so different values must be explored for each theme until the one that best fits the data is determined. Furthermore, it is considered that each document may contain several topics in particular proportions and that topics are not mutually exclusive categories, but rather combinations of words that may overlap within the same text (Piñeyrúa, 2021). Finally, it is understood that a document is a sequence of words, with each word corresponding to a meaningful unit of characters. This supports the probabilistic approach of the model (Rosati, 2022).

The LDA application procedure can be described broadly in five stages. First, the corpus is preprocessed to unify the format, segment the information and eliminate stop words, retaining only the most relevant terms. Next, processing is carried out to establish a k value and construct the Document-Term Matrix (DTM), which records the frequency with which words occur. Thirdly, models with different k values are compared and the most appropriate one is selected based on metrics such as consistency. Once the model has been chosen, topics are labelled by assigning categories to groups of words based on their frequency and context. Finally, the documents are classified according to their estimated thematic proportions, enabling the analysis of dynamics and variations in the corpus.

In technical terms, implementing this procedure in R requires specialized libraries. *Tidyverse* is used for data manipulation and organization; *topicmodels* for fitting Dirichlet latent assignment models; and *ggplot2* for graphically representing the results. *ldatuning* is used to evaluate the consistency between models. These libraries facilitate the exploration and interpretation of the analyzed information.

Annex III: Random Forest (RF)

Full method description

Random Forest (RF) is a supervised classification technique that combines multiple decision trees using a learning strategy called bagging. This involves training each tree with a different sample of data to produce more stable and accurate predictions (Pal, 2007; Barik et al., 2021; Pandey et al., 2024). RF works by generating a set of trees, each of which contributes a vote, and the final decision is obtained by aggregating these results. This methodology increases the robustness of the model by reducing variance and avoiding overfitting. Relevant attributes are selected using a predetermined probability, enabling the variables with the greatest weight in the model to be identified (Jackins et al., 2021). The most important parameters are *n*tree, which defines the number of trees in the forest, and *m*try, which determines how many variables are used to construct each tree (Phan et al., 2019). In practice, the greater the number of trees, the more robust and accurate the overall prediction will be (Wang et al., 2021).

Random Forest has several key advantages. It can handle large volumes of data with numerous variables, maintains good performance even with incomplete or noisy information, and provides measures of variable importance to help interpret the results. It also achieves high levels of accuracy and stability. However, it has some disadvantages: it can be less efficient in contexts where models require detailed interpretability, since the set of trees makes it difficult to visualize clear rules. In addition, the computational cost increases significantly as the number of trees increases (Phan et al., 2019).

The model is based on several fundamental assumptions. Firstly, individual decision trees are considered to be weak classifiers that, when combined, generate a strong classifier. Second, it is assumed that the variability introduced by the random selection of data and variables improves the model's generalization and avoids overfitting. Finally, it is understood that accuracy increases with the number of trees, provided they are constructed relatively independently (Wang et al., 2021).

The Random Forest application involves a series of general steps. First, the classification categories that will guide the supervised analysis are defined. In this case, these are loss and gain frames, as well as a neutral category. Next, a database is created containing news items that have been classified into the aforementioned categories. This enables the model to be trained using reliable data. The RF model is then constructed using this database, with parameters such as the number of trees and the variables considered being specified. Once the model has been trained, it is applied to the entire corpus to automatically assign labels to each document. Finally,

the results are interpreted using performance indicators that evaluate both the classification capacity of the model and the quality of the assigned probabilities.

First, accuracy measures the percentage of correct predictions by the model, that is, how many observations were correctly classified relative to the total. The Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) AUC (Area Under the Curve) value evaluates the model's ability to discriminate between classes, where values close to 1 reflect high separation power and values close to 0.5 indicate performance similar to chance. The Brier score quantifies the degree of calibration of probabilistic predictions by measuring the difference between the probabilities estimated by the model and the observed outcomes; low values for this metric indicate that the assigned probabilities are consistent with empirical reality.

In technical terms, the implementation of Random Forest in the R environment relies on specialized libraries. The `randomForest` library is the central tool for model construction and automatic classification, while `tidyverse` is used for data preparation and manipulation, and `ggplot2` facilitates the visualization of results and performance metrics. This set of libraries enables a comprehensive process that combines data preparation, application of the technique, and interpretation of results in an efficient and reproducible manner.

Annex IV: Bibliographic coupling (BC) for thematic analysis of papers

The analysis of scientific papers through BC comprises the following steps

1. **Search strategy**
2. **Download and parsing**
3. **Bibliographic coupling (BC)**

Bibliographic Coupling (BC) is a technique developed by Kessler (1963) that is based on the premise that two articles that share references are cognitively linked (Grauwin and Jensen, 2011; Kessler, 1963).

Using BC, a network is created using the retrieved articles as nodes and their "bibliographic coupling" (BC) as links. The strength of bibliographic coupling is defined as the number of shared references between two articles. It is possible to establish a minimum threshold of shared references to consider the existence of a link, which makes it possible to avoid artificial connections generated by excessively common references and to discard articles that were retrieved in the search due to methodological errors. In this work, we used two shared references to form the clusters.

The result is a network composed of records connected by shared references, while articles that do not share at least two references with any other document in the database are discarded at this stage.

The Louvain algorithm (Blondel et al., 2008) was then used to maximize modularity and identify a number of clusters with more than Y articles (in this work, we set this threshold at 100), a threshold established based on the population size. These clusters, defined by shared references, can in turn be linked to each other with varying intensities. Those most strongly linked generally represent subfields relevant to the research underway. These loose clusters are often destined for elimination due to their lack of thematic relevance.

In an iteration of the method, subclusters can be obtained, i.e., the internal clusters of each cluster, which are also composed of different shared reference parameters and cluster sizes.

In this work, we use two levels of clustering: the first defines the thematic structure, while the second is used for interpretive purposes, as it allows for a better understanding of the topics that comprise a larger cluster.

4. Interpretation of clusters

The clusters obtained, although they group articles that share common references, do not have intrinsic meaning. They must be interpreted. For example, a cluster may contain articles that have been grouped because they share the same methodology or because they use the same theoretical framework, and others that focus on the same analytical object without any theoretical or methodological links. Additionally, there are many characteristics of the texts that make up the clusters that must be understood in order to make sense of them.

To interpret the clusters, data mining techniques are used to obtain systematic sets of information about each cluster, as well as the general statistical measures that characterize each cluster with respect to the general population of texts analyzed.

These datasets allow each cluster to be assigned elements that facilitate interpretation, such as the average age of the papers comprising each cluster, the countries of the authors, the main keywords, the main words in the titles and abstracts, the most frequently used institutions, among others.

In this way, datasets associated with each cluster are constructed that allow for interpretation and include at least the following elements: Authors; Years of Publication; Citations; Keywords; Title Words; Journals; Topics; Countries; Institutions; References.

For each of these data sets, statistics are obtained that allow us to assess the frequency of appearance of an element within a cluster and also the specificity of its appearance within a cluster relative to the entire database.

At the same time, by assessing frequency and significance, a list of the most representative, most frequently cited, and most cited papers in a cluster can be compiled for downloading and further reading.

In this way, bibliographic coupling can provide new insights into the information provided by previous bibliometric studies and a more complex picture of the field's output. Unlike bibliometric studies, which often focus solely on the quantity of output, languages in which it is written, and main authors, this methodology allows for a more complex analysis and a visualization of the main discussions in this area. This methodology not only allows us to differentiate the predominant thematic areas and

changes in the dynamics of the field, but also opens the door to identifying less-explored or emerging research niches, which could guide future lines of study.

Additionally, data triangulation and other qualitative interpretation strategies such as interviews and consultations with specialists are used, along with the use of artificial intelligence.

Annex V: News Analysis: Mexico and Argentina

1. LDA Analysis

For the analysis of news from Mexico (588) and Argentina (454) from 2005 to 2024, tests were conducted with different numbers of topics ($k=3$ to $k=10$), selecting the model with the best balance between semantic coherence, thematic differentiation, and interpretability. The analysis was based on γ (gamma) values, which represent the estimated proportion of each topic in the documents, and β (beta) values, which indicate the probability of association of words with the topics. This made it possible to identify the temporal evolution of the topics and characterize their content. Thematic labels were defined by combining statistical criteria (γ and β values) and a qualitative analysis of the media context.

Figure I: Temporal dynamics of GH News in Argentina and Mexico (2005-2024)

1.1. México

For Mexico, the model with $k=4$ topics was selected because it presented the greatest coherence (0.36), indicating optimal thematic definition. This choice is based on the fact that models with $k<4$ show insufficient thematic diversity, while $k>4$ introduces redundancy by decreasing coherence.

Figure II: LDA Models for México (k=3 to k=10)

Table I: γ values (gamma) for k=4

Year	News	Topic 1	Topic 2	Topic 3	Topic 4
2005	1	1	0	0	0
2007	1	1	0	0	0
2008	2	0.995	0.005	0	0
2011	3	0.36	0.354	0.286	0
2012	3	0.642	0.358	0	0
2013	3	1	0	0	0
2014	4	1	0	0	0
2015	2	1	0	0	0
2016	3	1	0	0	0
2017	6	1	0	0	0
2018	5	1	0	0	0
2019	2	0.906	0.079	0.015	0
2020	23	0.699	0.246	0.055	0
2021	112	0.575	0.425	0	0
2022	110	1	0	0	0
2023	172	0.548	0.452	0	0
2024	136	1	0	0	0

Table II: β values (beta) for k=4

Topic	Words (beta)	Label
1	administration (0.0101), sciences (0.00735), executive (0.00642), companies (0.00524), law (0.00447)	Business Administration and Sciences
2	energy (0.0118), countries (0.00598), gas (0.00515), development (0.00434), natural (0.00428)	Energy and Natural Resources
3	production (0.00459), investment (0.00361), Pemex (0.00328), energy-related (0.00294), sector (0.00268)	Production and Energy Sector
4	lithium (0.00425), industry (0.00332), fuel (0.00307), vehicles (0.00293), project (0.00284)	Projects and Materials Technology

1.2. Argentina:

In the analysis of Argentina, the model with k=5 topics proved to be optimal, achieving the maximum coherence peak (0.85). This configuration marginally outperforms k=4 in topic quality and avoids the degradation observed in models with k>5.

Figure III: LDA Models for Argentina (k=3 to k=10)

Table III: γ values (gamma) for k=5

Year	News	Topic 1	Topic 2	Topic 3	Topic 4	Topic 5
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2005	6	0	0	0	0	1
2006	2	0	0	0.876	0.124	0
2007	3	0	0	1	0	0
2008	2	0	0	0	0	1
2010	2	0	0	1	0	0
2015	1	1	0	0	0	0
2016	2	0	0	0	0	1
2017	7	0	0	1	0	0
2018	3	0	0	0	0	1
2019	5	0	0	1	0	0
2020	15	0.008	0.96	0	0	0.032
2021	113	0.953	0	0.047	0	0
2022	125	0	0	0	1	0
2023	131	0	0	1	0	0
2024	37	0	0	0	0.393	.607

Table IV: β values (beta) for k=5

Tema	Palabras (beta)	Etiqueta
1	development (0.00543), government (0.00485), energy (0.00413), production (0.00413), economy (0.00333)	Economic Development and Energy
2	projects (0.00396), national (0.00374), gas (0.00366), investments (0.00328), change (0.00288)	National Projects and Investments
3	province (0.00505), investment (0.00460), objective (0.00395), plant (0.00371), companies (0.00361)	Regional Investment and Companies
4	sector (0.00288), labor (0.00256), Ukraine (0.00230), major (0.00224), law (0.00217)	Labor and Legislative Sector
5	market (0.00394), RIGI (0.00356), Milei (0.00296), industry (0.00290), YPF (0.00216)	Energy Market and Industry

2. Random Forest: News analysis of Imaginaries and technoscientific promises

The Random Forest (RF) algorithm was used to automatically classify news stories about green hydrogen into three categories: promises of origin, promises of receipt, and none. The same dataset of news stories was used by country. A second layer of the model was then added to separate the stories by positive, negative, and neutral sentiment.

2.1. México

To evaluate the performance of the Random Forest model, we worked with a database of 588 news items, of which 70.7% were classified as promises (416 cases), 25% as none (147 cases), and 4.25% as responses (25 cases). Coding was performed using a representative sample with a 95% confidence level and a 5% margin of error. The results show an accuracy of 0.755, indicating that the model correctly classifies three-quarters of the cases; a multiclass AUC of 0.843, reflecting a high ability to discriminate between categories; and a Brier score of 0.215, indicating a lower calibration in the predicted probabilities, although with good overall discriminatory performance.

Figure IV: Random Forest Model in Mexico: Promises of origin and reception promises

Within these categories, a total of 864 mentions were identified, of which 826 were promises and 38 were responses. These were organized into six main categories: environmental, clean energy, public infrastructure, legislative, economic, and employment.

The environmental category was the most frequent, with 448 promises (340 positive, 14 negative, and 94 neutral) and 21 responses (19 positive and 2 neutral). The clean energy category followed, with 216 promises (157 positive, 10 negative, and 49 neutral) and 10 responses (9 positive and 1 neutral). Public infrastructure had 83 promises (60 positive, 2 negative, and 21 neutral) and 1 positive response. The legislative dimension totaled 49 promises (33 positive, 1 negative, and 15 neutral) and 5 positive responses. The economic category contained 26 promises (17

positive, 2 negative, and 7 neutral) and 1 positive response. Finally, in the employment category, 4 promises were identified (2 positive, 1 negative, and 1 neutral), with no recorded responses.

In terms of orientation, the promises were predominantly positive (609), with a smaller number of neutral (178) and negative (39) mentions. The responses were also predominantly positive (35), with 3 neutral and no negative ones.

In terms of time, mentions began to appear dispersedly between 2004 and 2020, with low frequencies, mainly between 1 and 9 mentions per year. Starting in 2021, a sustained increase in the number of references is observed. In 2021, there were 89 mentions, in 2022 there were 118, in 2023 there were 182, and in 2024 the peak was recorded with 197 mentions. This increase was concentrated mainly in the environmental and clean energy categories. Responses also intensified during this same recent period, particularly between 2022 and 2024.

2.2. Argentina

The Random Forest model was applied to a corpus of 458 news items, in which 85.6% were classified as promises (392 cases), 8.73% as none (40 cases), and 5.68% as responses (26 cases). The model achieved an accuracy of 0.779, meaning it correctly predicted almost eight out of ten cases, although with a tighter performance than in other datasets. The multiclass AUC value was 0.599, reflecting a limited discrimination capacity between categories, with less differentiated predictions. The Brier score of 0.181 indicates a moderate level of error in the calibration of probabilities, suggesting that the model requires improvements in the representation of minority classes and preprocessing adjustments to achieve greater robustness.

Figure V: Randon Forest Model in Argentina: *Promises of origin and reception promises*

Within these categories, a total of 414 mentions were identified, of which 404 corresponded to promises and 10 to responses. These were organized around five main categories: clean energy, employment, environmental, economic, and public infrastructure.

The clean energy category was the most frequent, with 311 promises (124 positive and 187 negative) and 3 responses (2 positive and 1 negative). The employment category followed, with 51 promises (18 positive and 33 negative), with no recorded responses. The environmental category accumulated 16 promises (3 positive and 13 negative) and 3 responses (2 positive and 1 negative). In the economic dimension, 15 promises (6 positive and 9 negative) and 4 responses (3 positive and 1 negative) were identified. Public infrastructure totaled 11 promises (5 positive and 6 negative), with no responses.

Regarding their focus, the promises showed a majority of negative mentions (248) compared to positive ones (156). The responses, although few, were distributed as follows: 9 positive mentions and 1 negative mention.

Over time, mentions remained low and sporadic between 2004 and 2020, with no more than 10 per year. A significant increase was observed starting in 2021: 116 mentions were recorded in 2021, 128 in 2022, 154 in 2023, and a slight decrease in 2024, with 61 mentions. This increase was especially concentrated in the clean energy category, followed by employment and environmental issues. Responses were also concentrated in the 2021–2024 period, particularly in 2023 and 2024.

Table V: valuative analysis (positive/negative) of promises of origin and reception promises

Label	Country	Type	Positive	Negative	Neutral	Total
Clean energy	Argentina	Promises of origin	124	187	–	311
		Reception promises	2	1	–	3
	México	Promises of origin	157	10	49	216
		Reception promises	9	0	1	10
Environmental	Argentina	Promises of origin	3	13	–	16

		Reception promises		2	1	–	3
	México	Promises of origin		340	14	94	448
		Reception promises		19	0	2	21
Employment	Argentina	Promises of origin		18	33	–	51
		Reception promises		0	0	–	0
	México	Promises of origin		2	1	1	4
		Reception promises		0	0	0	0
Economic	Argentina	Promises of origin		6	9	–	15
		Reception promises		3	1	–	4
	México	Promises of origin		17	2	7	26
		Reception promises		1	0	0	1
Public infrastructure	Argentina	Promises of origin		5	6	–	11
		Reception promises		0	0	–	0
	México	Promises of origin		60	2	21	83
		Reception promises		1	0	0	1
Policies	Argentina	Reception promises		–	–	–	–
		Promises of origin		–	–	–	–
	México	Promises of origin		33	1	15	49

		Reception promises	5	0	0	5
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Figure VI: promises of origin and reception promises in Argentina (left) and Mexico (right) 2005-2024

Annex VI: Análisis temático de los papers e identificación de Imaginarios y promesas:

1. Bibliographic Coupling Analysis

1.1. Search strategy

We used a search strategy that contains the main topic in English and Spanish.

We look for articles that contains the keywords in the title or the abstract. The query for Web of Science (and the adaptations for other databases was: (((TI="Hidrógeno verde") OR (AB=Hidrógeno verde")) AND ((TI="green hydrogen") OR (AB="green hydrogen"))))

We opted for the most inclusive search strategy possible. On the one hand, it is better to have a large number of documents and discard the irrelevant ones than to skew the search sample, since it is impossible to analyse what has been excluded. On the other hand, our clustering method is powerful and reliable enough to enable us to obtain robust thematic clusters and eliminate documents that cannot be linked to the set. Through an iterative process of the methodology, we have verified that robust sets of information are obtained.

This search yielded 4,060 results in Web of Science, 6,173 in OpenAlex and 4,644 in SCOPUS, bringing the total number of results to 14,877.

1.2. Download and parsing

After downloading the records from the three databases, we cleaned them, eliminating duplicates and merging the databases. We then sorted the data for further processing, leaving us with a total of 13,146 papers.

1.3. Bibliographic coupling (BC)

La estructura de cluster y subclusters obtenida, es la siguiente

Table I: structure of clusters and subclusters

	WEB OF SCIENCE	OPEN ALEX	SCOPUS
Articles	4063	6173	4644
Clusters (+100; 2 shr)	4	5	6
Subclusters (+50, 2 shr)	23	31	17

The clusters were obtained considering a minimum size of 100 articles and a minimum of 2 shared references (shr), while the subclusters were obtained considering a minimum size of 50 articles and 2 shr.

1.4. Interpretation

To understand the content of each cluster, several bibliometric analyses were performed to compile the most frequent and significant keywords, authors, title words, countries, institutions and the most representative and most cited papers of each cluster and subcluster.

This data, together with a thorough reading of the selected papers, enables us to interpret and validate the content of the clusters.

1.4.1. BC Cluster description

Cluster Storage-ENERGY

The sources primarily discuss the technical and economic aspects of green hydrogen production, including costs, efficiency, and the technological maturity of electrolyzers and fuel cells, compared to traditional fossil-fuel-based methods. In addition, the challenges and barriers (technical, economic, social, political, and regulatory) to the widespread adoption of hydrogen are addressed. The potential applications of hydrogen in various sectors such as transportation (vehicles, aviation, trains, ships), industry (chemicals, steel), and domestic heating are also a central topic, exploring its environmental impact in terms of CO₂ emissions reduction and the integration of the entire value chain, from production to end-use.

Cluster Electrocatalysis-WATER (Tema 3 LDA)

The sources focus on electrocatalysis for water splitting as a strategy for hydrogen production. Emphasis is placed on the design of stable, high-performance electrocatalysts, both made of noble and non-noble metals, through materials engineering. Key strategies for improving performance include electronic structure modulation, surface engineering, the use of hierarchical structures (1D, 3D) to maximize surface area, enhance charge and mass transport, and facilitate gas release,

and the development of self-supporting electrodes on conductive substrates such as nickel foam. Other technical aspects of catalyst performance are discussed.

Cluster Electrolysis-WATER

Several water electrolysis technologies are discussed in depth, including proton exchange membrane water electrolysis (PEMWE), alkaline water electrolysis (AWE), anion exchange membrane water electrolysis (AEMWE), and solid oxide electrolysis (SOEC). Key topics cover the challenges associated with cost reduction (especially for PEMWE due to noble metal and titanium components) and the durability and degradation of key components. Research focuses on the development of efficient and low-cost electrocatalysts (especially platinum group metal-free), membrane improvements (stability, conductivity, and fluorine-free materials), and the optimization of porous transport layers (PTLs) for improved mass, charge, and heat transfer. Furthermore, the need for holistic and data-driven approaches to optimize the levelized cost of green hydrogen under dynamic operation is underlined.

Cluster Production-SOLAR

The sources converge on the fundamental challenge of achieving sustainable green hydrogen production and CO₂ valorization through solar conversion processes. Various technologies for solar water splitting are discussed, including photoelectrochemical cells (PECs), photocatalytic (PC) systems, and combined photovoltaics-electrolysis (PV-EC). A recurring theme is the critical need to improve the efficiency, stability, and durability of these systems, along with the challenge of scaling them up from laboratory to commercial scale. Key strategies to overcome these obstacles revolve around materials engineering, seeking semiconductors with optimal light absorption, charge separation, and transport properties, often through morphological control, doping, and surface modification with cocatalysts such as Pt, Rh, IrO₂, or MoS₂ to enhance catalytic activity and suppress recombination. Furthermore, the importance of advanced reactor design that considers factors such as light distribution, mass transfer, and gas separation is highlighted. Some research also explores the use of sacrificial electron donors, such as biomass or waste, to boost hydrogen production, and the conversion of CO₂ into fuels such as methanol or jet fuel, involving the use of bimetallic catalysts and metal oxides. Overall, the sources emphasize the need for a deep understanding of fundamental mechanisms and the development of theoretical simulations and advanced characterization techniques to guide innovation.

Cluster Ammonia-ENERGY

Production methods, particularly through electrolysis and ammonia cracking, highlight the need for sustainable and low-carbon approaches. A significant portion of the information focuses on the challenges and diverse technologies for hydrogen and ammonia storage and transport, including compressed gas (CGH₂), liquid hydrogen (LH₂), liquid organic hydrogen carriers (LOHC), and large-scale geological storage such as salt caverns and aquifers.

Cluster China-ENERGY

Sources converge on the discussion of carbon neutrality and peak CO₂ emissions targets as a global consensus, with a particular focus on China's challenges and strategies to achieve these goals by 2060.

2. Analysis of sociotechnical imaginaries and technoscientific promises in Papers: abstracts

To create the RF models, a representative sample of 15% of each dataset was coded through the complete reading of the papers, totaling 14,235 abstracts (including clusters and subclusters). The 12 categories established as GH promises were considered, and a "none" category was added, coding 164 texts (abstracts) for each category. The model was trained using Random Forest with 1,000 trees, tokenization and TF-IDF were applied for text preprocessing, and the maximum number of tokens was limited to 150. A 5-fold stratified cross-validation was used, with node-by-node variable tuning and a minimum of 5 observations per node to avoid overfitting. The expected performance of the model included an accuracy of 0.779, a multiclass AUC of 0.599, and a Brier score of 0.181, reflecting a moderate discrimination and probability calibration capacity. The results were organized by category and year.

Table II: Imaginaries and Promises found in papers

Imaginaries	Promises	Frequency
1. Technoscientific	1.1 Techno-scientific	1562
2. Economic	2.1 Production	707
	2.2 Local development & Integration	501
	2.3 Infrastructure	1160
3. Politic	3.1 Employment	1513
	3.2 Administration	3726
	3.3 Industrial policy	486
4. Environmental	4.1 Environmental	1323
5. Energetic	5.1 Clean energy	329
6. Geopolitic	6.1 Investments & Projects	1092
	6.2 International insertion	804
	6.3 Climate commitments	1232

References

Barik, S., Mohanty, S., Rout, D., Mohanty, S., Patra, A., & Mishra, A. (2021). Heart disease prediction using machine learning techniques. In *Advances in Electrical Control and Signal Systems: Select Proceedings of AECSS 2019* (pp. 879-888). Springer Singapore.

Bird, S., Klein, E., & Loper, E. (2009). *Natural language processing with Python*. O'Reill

Blei, D., Ng, A., & Jordan, M. (2003). Latent Dirichlet Allocation. *Journal of Machine Learning Research*, 3, 993-1022. <https://jmlr.csail.mit.edu/papers/v3/blei03a.html>

Blondel, V., Guillaume, J.-L., Lambiotte, R., & Lefebvre, E. (2008). Fast unfolding of communities in large networks. *Journal of Statistical Mechanics: Theory and Experiment*, 2008(10), P10008.

Ejaz, W., Ittefaq, M., & Jamil, S. (2023). Politics triumphs: A topic modeling approach for analyzing news media coverage of climate change in Pakistan. *Journal of Science Communication*, 22(1), A02. <https://doi.org/10.22323/2.22010202>

Grauwin, S., & Jensen, P. (2011). Mapping scientific institutions. *Scientometrics*, 89(3), 943-954.

Grün, B., & Hornik, K. (2011). topicmodels: An R package for fitting topic models. *Journal of statistical software*, 40, 1-30. <https://doi.org/10.18637/jss.v040.i13>

Jackins, V., Vimal, S., Kaliappan, M., & Lee, M. Y. (2021). AI-based smart prediction of clinical disease using random forest classifier and Naive Bayes. *The Journal of Supercomputing*, 77(5), 5198-5219. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11227-020-03481-x>

Kessler, M. M. (1963). Bibliographic coupling between scientific papers. *American Documentation*, 14(1), 10-25. <https://doi.org/10.1002/asi.5090140103>

Piñeyrúa, F. (2021). Aportes desde el procesamiento de lenguaje natural para incrementar la escalabilidad en los estudios sobre tópicos de noticias digitales securitarias. *Revista Comunicación, Política y Seguridad*, (3), 111-142. <https://publicaciones.sociales.uba.ar/index.php/revistacomunicacion/article/view/6627>

Pal, M. (2007). Random forest classifier for remote sensing classification. *International Journal of Remote Sensing*, 26(1), 217–222. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01431160412331269698>

Pandey, R., Upadhyaya, M., & Singh, M. (2024). Rainfall Prediction Using Logistic Regression and Random Forest Algorithm. In *2024 IEEE International Conference on Computing, Power and Communication Technologies (IC2PCT)* (Vol. 5, pp. 663-668). IEEE.

Phan, D., Nguyen, N., Pathirana, P. N., Horne, M., Power, L., & Szmulewicz, D. (2019). A random forest approach for quantifying gait ataxia with truncal and peripheral measurements using multiple wearable sensors. *IEEE Sensors Journal*, 20(2), 723-734. <http://doi.org/10.1109/JSEN.2019.2943879>

Rosati, D. (2022). Moving beyond word lists: Towards abstractive topic labels for human-like topics of scientific documents. En *Proceedings of the First Workshop on Information Extraction from Scientific Publications* (pp. 91–99). Association for Computational Linguistics. <https://doi.org/10.18653/v1/2022.wiesp-1.11>

Wang, F., Wang, Y., Zhang, K., Hu, M., Weng, Q., & Zhang, H. (2021). Spatial heterogeneity modeling of water quality based on random forest regression and model interpretation. *Environmental Research*, 202, 111660. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2021.111660>